

Updating Fe IX energy levels for CHIANTI 10.1

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Ryabtsev et al. (2022, ApJ) provided some new energies for the $3p^43d^2$ configuration, and this document explains the decisions made in adding these to the CHIANTI 10 model, in preparation for the CHIANTI 10.1 release.

R22 listed 45 levels. Fifteen have calculated energies and these were not added to the CHIANTI model. Three levels had questionable identifications as only a single transition was identified from the level, and these were not used. Five levels were already in the CHIANTI model, and the new energies were only marginally different to the existing ones (which were updated).

The remaining 22 levels are discussed individually below.

Six level energies were rejected and not added to the CHIANTI model. This does not imply the Ryabtsev energies are incorrect, but they may not be consistent with the CHIANTI atomic model, or the evidence was considered not sufficient to make the identification.

At the end of the document is a comparison of predicted and observed Fe IX intensities from Hinode/EIS (LY09) for the 170-212 Å range using the new line identifications. Agreement is generally good, giving confidence in the new line identifications.

Key

R22	Ryabtsev et al. (2022, ApJ)
DZ14	Del Zanna (2014, A&A)
YL09	Young & Landi (2009, ApJ)
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Index 99, 1F3

The strongest decay is to level 9 (1D2), with additional decays to levels 7 (3F2; 44%), 8 (3D3; 6%), 11 (3D2; 17%) and 12 (1F3; 16%). R22 list all of these except the decay to level 11. The decay to level 7 (188.30 Å) is blended with Fe XI. The strongest line is at 196.805 Å and the line in the LY09 atlas at this position has an intensity distribution consistent with Fe IX. I accept this identification.

Index 103, 3F2

The strongest decay is to level 10 (3D1), with additional decays to levels 6 (3F3, 7%) and 7 (3F2; 68%). R22 identify the decays to levels 10 and 7 and the intensity ratio is consistent with the A-values. The strongest line is at 195.733 Å, consistent with a line in the LY09 spectrum that has an intensity distribution consistent with Fe IX. I accept this identification.

Index 105, 3F4

The strongest decay is to level 8 (3D3), with additional decays to levels 5 (3F4; 60%), 12 (1F3; 17%) and 6 (3F3; 7%). R22 list three lines, with only the 3F3 decay not listed. This level had previously been tentatively identified by DZ14.

The strongest line at 192.633 Å is listed as a blend with Fe XI. The Fe XI line should be 0.33 of the line at 201.734, which is definitely a Fe XI line. However, the branching ratio suggests the 192.6 should be dominated by Fe XI, yet the image formed in this line (for the LY09 dataset) is clearly dominated by Fe IX. This suggests the Fe XI branching ratio may not be correct.

The next strongest line is at 182.161 Å which is a blend with Fe XI 182.167 Å. The latter is a strong line and the image does not show any evidence of an Fe IX component.

Assuming the 192.633 Å line has a negligible contribution from Fe XI, then the branching ratio to level 1F3 is consistent with the A-values.

I accept this identification.

Index 106, 3F3

The strongest decay is to level 11 (3D2), with additional decays to levels 7 (3F2; 15%), 8 (3D3; 8%), 9 (1D2; 17%), and 6 (3F3; 54%). R22 list all five of these lines and the intensities are reasonable. The strongest line is at 194.796 Å and there's clearly an Fe IX line at this wavelength in the LY09 spectrum based on the intensity image. However, the predicted intensity is about a factor two weaker than that measured by LY09. This is because of a blend with Fe VII 194.771. The Fe VII and Fe IX lines cannot be resolved at the EIS resolution, but they are resolved in the laboratory spectra (Fig. 3 of Young et al. 2021, ApJ).

The next strongest line 182.919 Å cannot be seen in the EIS spectrum, but sensitivity is low here. The 192.182 Å seems to be present, however, although the A-value suggests it should be weak.

I accept this identification.

Index 109, 3S1

The strongest decay is to level 3P1, with additional decays to levels 4 (3P2; 34%) and 2 (3P0; 53%). R22 list all three lines, but the decays to 3P1 and 3P0 are listed as blends with other Fe IX lines. The strength of the unblended line suggests the 3S1 decays make minor contributions to these blends.

The 174.024 Å line (strongest from 3S1) is blended with the 8-124 transition. The CHIANTI model suggests the latter should be stronger by a factor 5. This is consistent with the R22 intensity.

The 175.648 Å line (weakest from 3S1) is blended with the 8-126 transition. The CHIANTI model suggests the latter should be stronger by a factor 6. This is consistent with the R22 intensity.

The EIS spectra are not useful for these lines due to low sensitivity.

In comparison with other nearby levels, the observed-theoretical energy difference is large (5000 cm⁻¹).

I reject this identification as the evidence is inconclusive.

Index 112, 3D1

The strongest decay is to level 7 (3F2) and all other decays are less than 5%. R22 identified the 3F2 decay and also the decay to level 4 (3P2) which is predicted to be only 0.8%.

YL09 were not able to identify the 7-112 transition as there were two options in the EIS spectrum: lines at 178.71 and 178.99 Å. As discussed below (index 118), the latter line is a decay from level 118, hence it's reasonable to assign the former line to level 112, even though the 4-112 identification is questionable.

I accept this identification.

Index 113, 1G4

The strongest decay is to level 12 (1F3) and the only other significant decay is to level 8 (3D3; 15%). R22 identify both of these lines and also the decay to 3F4 (0.8%). The latter is very weak, but plausible. The decay to level 8 at 185.244 Å is blended with Fe VIII.

The strongest line at 188.818 matches a line in the LY09 spectrum that is usually identified with Ar XI 188.806 Å, but the image is more consistent with Fe IX. Note that 188.818/188.493 is a nice density diagnostic. The high density limit (which is relevant to the lab spectrum of R22) is about 0.5, consistent with the R22 measurements.

I accept this identification.

Index 114, 3P0

The only significant decay is to level 3 (3P1), and this is listed by R22 but with a question mark.

I reject this identification.

Index 115, 3P2

The strongest decay is to level 4 (3P2), with additional decays to levels 12 (1F3; 12%) and 3 (3P1; 39%). R22 list the two stronger lines. The strongest line (171.685 Å) is given as a blend with Fe VII. The CHIANTI model suggests 171.685 should be about 0.3 of the nearby 169.914 Å, but the R22 intensity is stronger than expected. The 4-115 transition (170.116 Å) is stronger than expected.

This identification is not convincing to me, so I reject it.

Index 116, 3P1

The strongest decay is to level 4 (3P2), with additional decays to levels 2 (3P0; 23%) and 3 (3P1; 6%). R22 list these lines as well as the decay to 3F2, which is listed as a blend with another Fe IX line. The strongest line at 171.706 Å is listed as a blend with Fe VII. The CHIANTI model predicts that it's about the same strength as the 3P2-3P2 transition at 171.861 (see index 115).

The decay to 3P0 is unblended and the intensity seems OK. The decay to 3P1 is listed as a wide line, and the intensity is too high.

I also note that the observed-theoretical differences are quite large for the 3P0 to 3P2 levels (114-116).

I reject this identification.

Index 117 or 120, 1D2

There are two 1D2 levels with theoretical energies in CHIANTI of 1000488 and 1022804 cm^{-1} , and R22 identify a 1D2 level with energy 1017204. It's thus more likely that the R22 level corresponds to the higher energy level (120). The R22 level is highly mixed.

The strongest decay is to level 9 (1D2) with additional decays to levels 7 (3F2; 61%), 8 (3D3; 90%), 10 (3D1; 28%), 12 (1F3; 55%) and 3 (3P1; 17%). R22 list three lines, with decays to 3D3, 1D2 and 1F3. However, the expected strongest line (from CHIANTI) is significantly weaker in the lab spectrum and R22's atomic model.

If we switch to level 117, this doesn't help as the decay to 1D2 is also strong here.

Since the transitions from this level are all weak compared to other Fe IX lines, and the level is highly mixed, *I reject this identification.*

Index 118, 3F4

The strongest decay is to level 5 (3F4) with further decays to levels 8 (3D3; 20%), 12 (1F3; 5%) and 6 (3F3; 9%). R22 list all four of these lines. Note that the decay to 3F4 (169.914 Å) is one of the strongest Fe IX lines, comparable in strength to the 176.945 and 188.493 lines.

The decay to 3F3 is listed by R22 as a blend with another Fe IX line (from level 121), and the decay to 1F3 is listed as a blend with an unknown species.

I accept this identification and note that the decay to 3D3 gives the line at 178.972 Å, which helps in the identification of lines from level 112 (see above).

Index 121, 3F3

The strongest decay is to level 6 (3F3), with additional decays to levels 7 (3F2; 14%), 4 (3P2; 8%), 9 (1D2; 11%) and 11 (3D2; 19%). R22 list all of these except the decay to 3P2, and also list the decay to level 5 (3F4; 2%). The strongest line (169.614 Å) is unblended. The decay to 3F2 is a blend with another Fe IX line (6-128), and the decay to 3D2 is a blend with Fe XI. The decay to 1D2 is unblended and the intensity is reasonable.

I accept this identification.

Index 123, 3F2

The strongest decay is to level 7 (3F2) with additional decays to levels 6 (3F3; 9%), 8 (3D3; 6%), 10 (3D1; 36%), and 9 (1D2; 29%). R22 list all of these lines, and also have the decay to level 3 (3P1; 0.5%). The lines are all fairly weak, and the strongest (169.773 Å) is listed as a blend with Fe VII.

The observed-theoretical energy difference is reasonably consistent with 3F3 and 3F4 levels of the same multiplet.

I accept this identification.

Index 124, 3D3

The strongest decay is to level 8 (3D3) with additional decays to levels 4 (3P2; 24%) and 12 (1F3; 17%). R22 list the two strongest lines. The strongest at 174.024 is a blend with another Fe

IX line (3-109), although the CHIANTI model predicts that it dominates. The 3P2 decay intensity is consistent.

I accept this identification.

Index 126, 3P2

The strongest decay is to level 8 (3D3), with additional decays to levels 9 (1D2; 20%), 11 (3D2; 44%) and 12 (1F3; 45%). R22 list three lines, with the 3D2 decay missing. The strongest line (175.648 Å) is listed as a blend with another Fe IX line (4-109), but is expected to be much stronger (see discussion on level 109). The intensities of the other two lines are then reasonably consistent.

I accept this identification.

Index 127, 3D1

The strongest decay is to level 10 (3D1) with additional decays to levels 2 (3P0; 7%) and 3 (3P1; 7%). R22 list the 3D1 and 3P0 decays, and the intensities are reasonable.

The observed-theoretical energy difference is consistent with the 3D3 level (124).

I accept this identification.

Index 129, 3D2

The strongest decay is to level 11 (3D2) with additional decays to levels 4 (3P2; 7%), 8 (3D3; 16%), 9 (1D2; 9%), 12 (1F3; 66%) and 3 (3P1; 15%). R22 list all 6 lines, and the intensities are reasonable.

The observed-theoretical energy difference is consistent with the 3D3 and 3D1 levels (124, 127).

I accept this identification.

Index 130, 3P1

The strongest decay is to level 11 (3D2) with additional decays to levels 9 (1D2; 8%) and 2 (3P0; 2%). R22 lists the strongest line and the decay to level 10 (3D1; 0.2%). The former is listed as a blend with Fe VII. The other has a much stronger A-value in R22's atomic model compared to CHIANTI.

The observed-theoretical energy difference is consistent with the 3P2 level (126).

I reject this identification.

Index 133, 1F3

The strongest decay is to level 12 (1F3), with additional decays to levels 8 (3D3; 4%), 9 (1D2; 14%) and 11 (3D2; 7%). R22 list all four lines. The strongest at 172.219 Å is quite strong and the intensity is reasonably consistent with, e.g., the 169.914 Å line. The other lines are stronger than expected.

I accept this identification.

Index 166, 1D2

The strongest decay is to level 13 (1P1) with additional decays to levels 9 (1D2; 18%) and 11 (3D2; 9%). R22 list each of these lines. The intensity of the stronger line is weaker than expected compared to the other two, although they have a wide wavelength separation (more than 30 Å), so calibration may be an issue. The stronger line corresponds to an Fe IX line in the EIS spectrum (YL09).

I accept this identification.

Comparison with EIS spectra

After inputting the new level energies into the CHIANTI 10 model, I now compare predicted intensities with the measured intensities from the LY09 paper. I use the DEM derived by LY09 and a density of 10^9 cm^{-3} to derive predicted line intensities ($\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ sr}^{-1}$).

The table below lists the strongest lines expected in the 170-212 Å region, taking into account the EIS effective area. The predicted intensities have been scaled to force the 197.854 intensity to be the same as the measured intensity (indicated by R in table below). Blends with known lines are indicated in the right column. Lines marked with an asterisk in Column 1 are lines identified as Fe IX transitions in YL09 (Table 10), but for which identifications could not be made at the time.

Wavelength	Indices	I_{pred}	I_{obs}
176.945	5-110	366	447
177.592	6-111	192	148
178.697	7-112	96	69
178.973	8-118	69	76
182.172	5-105	36	59 (b Fe X)
182.928	6-106	22	26
185.978*	7-103	11	19
187.950*	13-166	76	90
188.303	7-99	16	257 (b Fe IX)
188.493	5-96	447	376
188.680	5-95	24	32
188.817	12-113	48	43
189.572	6-97	26	8
189.935	6-95	267	237
191.206	7-97	111	105
192.630*	8-105	61	77 (b Fe XI)
194.796*	11-106	41	109 (b Fe VII)
195.733*	10-103	15	20

196.497	12-105	10	10 (b Fe XIII)
196.802*	9-99	36	35
197.854	13-148	188	188 (R)
199.100	11-199	6	6
199.975	9-97	11	48 (b Fe XIII)
200.381	12-99	6	17

Agreement between the predicted and observed intensities is generally good. The predicted 189.572 line is significantly stronger than observed. The 191.206 line (which has the same upper level) is in good agreement with observations, suggesting there is a problem with the branching ratio for the 189.572 line.

The table below lists the five strongest lines with theoretical wavelengths, all of which should be measurable in the EIS spectrum.

Wavelength	Indices	I _{pred}
190.059	8-108	44
195.807	4-85	79
196.115	2-82	19
196.356	3-83	24
198.614	5-87	26